

Uninsulated Pipes of Solar Water Heater Thermosyphonic System

by Joseph Nowarski, M.Sc., ME – Energy Conservation Expert

Version 1.1.2, 20 September 2017

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.17035871

all versions DOI:10.5281/zenodo.17035870

Abstract

Uninsulated pipes of solar water heaters in Israel increase national electricity consumption by 200 millions kWh/year, 40 millions USD per year. Simple solution having 2-4 months return of investment period can stop this waste.

This work introduces energy balance of thermosyphonic solar water heater (SWH) without pipes' thermal insulation. The results are used for economic evaluation.

Thermal insulation of SWH is required by solar legislation in Israel and national standards. Actually there is not any insulation on SWH pipes. Outside pipes' thermal insulation, if installed, is completely damaged after 1-2 years. Pipes inside buildings usually are in sleeve made of plastic pipe used for electric cables. Plastic sleeves on hot water supply pipes are good equivalent for thermal insulation. However lack of insulation or sleeve on outside circulation pipes increases need for backup resulting in huge national cost.

1. Glossary

E	energy [kcal] (not kcal/hr)
kcal	kilo-calorie, energy unit
PE	person, people equivalent
Q	energy in time [kcal/hr] (not kcal)
SE	Solar Energy
SWH	Solar Water Heater, in this work domestic solar water heater for residential units, thermosyphonic system
U	overall heat transfer coefficient [kcal/m ² ,hr,°C]
V	water flow [liter/hour]
XLPE	cross-linked Poly-Ethylene
α	thermal conductivity of laminar layer [kcal/m ² ,hr,°C]
λ	thermal conductivity, specific thermal conductivity of solid material [kcal/m,hr,°C]
ρ	density [kg/liter]

2. Introduction

Solar legislation in Israel requires installation of solar water heaters (SWH) in new buildings up to (down to) 9 floors from roof. The legislation and national standards require thermal insulation for hot water pipes [4].

Actually, there is not any insulation on SWH pipes. Outside pipes' thermal insulation, if installed, is completely damaged after 1-2 years. This results in increased electric backup.

This work is based on "*Energy Balance of Solar Water Heaters: Thermosyphonic Systems*" [1] and "*Heat Transfer in Solar Water Heaters Pipes: Thermosyphonic Systems*" [2].

These publications ([1] and [2]) allow to perform energy balance of SWH, determination of energy losses, including hot water pipes with any kind of insulation or without insulation, and, as the result, determination of electric backup required for any solution.

Pipes inside buildings usually are in sleeve made of plastic pipe used for electric cables, which is good alternative to thermal insulation.

This work is for thermosyphonic SWH with plastic pipes.

All conditions are for Israel so the results do not necessary apply to other countries.

Example of a typical installation in Israel

Circulation pipes in the above example are not insulated. Blue sleeve is on cold water supply pipe, while hot water supply pipe is not insulated and has no sleeve. Unfortunately, this example is typical for SWH in Israel.

3. Energy Units

This work is in Metric Units. Usually metric units apply Joule as energy unit. In this work the energy unit is kilocalorie, the energy required to heat 1 kg of water (1 liter) by 1°C. 1 kcal is equal to 4,186.8 Joule, and 1 kJ is equal to 0.23885 kcal. Application of kcal instead of Joule is very convenient for works involving water heating, as the temperature difference indicates immediately the amount of energy in kcal.

Electric energy is expressed in kWh.

1 kWh is 859.85 kcal and 1 kcal is 1.1630 Wh.

4. Energy Balance of Thermosyphonic SWH with Insulated Pipes

Publication [1] includes energy balance for thermosyphonic SWH with insulated pipes. Following is energy balance for plastic pipes option of the SWH.

Chart 1 - SWH losses, **insulated** plastic pipes

Table 1 - Energy balance of SWH **insulated** plastic pipes, kcal/day

Month	Demand	SE from collector	Calculated losses	other losses	SE in tap	need for backup	Total energy available	not used
	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d
1	6,083	4,921	836	743	3,343	2,741	6,083	0
2	6,328	6,024	1,010	743	4,271	2,057	6,328	0
3	5,587	6,506	1,094	743	4,670	917	5,587	0
4	4,546	7,010	1,134	743	4,546	0	5,134	588
5	3,623	7,418	1,228	743	3,623	0	5,448	1,825
6	3,107	7,618	1,260	743	3,107	0	5,615	2,509
7	2,771	7,637	1,264	743	2,771	0	5,630	2,859
8	2,591	7,886	1,291	743	2,591	0	5,853	3,261
9	3,150	7,865	1,271	743	3,150	0	5,852	2,702
10	3,354	7,103	1,141	743	3,354	0	5,220	1,866
11	4,823	6,027	1,014	743	4,270	553	4,823	0
12	5,426	4,924	829	743	3,352	2,074	5,426	0
Ave	4,282	6,745	1,114	743	3,587	695	5,583	1,301
	77%	121%	20%	13%	64%	12%	100%	23%

Table 2 - Energy balance of SWH **insulated** plastic pipes, kWh/month

Month	Demand	SE	Calculated losses	other losses	Available from SE	SE in tap	need for backup	Total energy available	not used
	kWh/month	kWh/month	kWh/month	kWh/month	kWh/month	kWh/month	kWh/month	kWh/month	kWh/month
1	219	177	30	27	121	121	99	219	0
2	206	196	33	24	139	139	67	206	0
3	201	235	39	27	168	168	33	201	0
4	159	245	40	26	179	159	0	179	20
5	131	267	44	27	196	131	0	196	66
6	108	266	44	26	196	108	0	196	88
7	100	275	46	27	203	100	0	203	103
8	93	284	47	27	211	93	0	211	118
9	110	274	44	26	204	110	0	204	94
10	121	256	41	27	188	121	0	188	67
11	168	210	35	26	149	149	19	168	0
12	196	178	30	27	121	121	75	196	0
Σ/y	1,813	2,864	473	315	2,076	1,520	293	2,369	556
	77%	121%	20%	13%	88%	64%	12%	100%	23%

Chart 2 - Energy balance of SWH **insulated** plastic pipes

5. Solar Water Heater

Solar water heater (SWH) analyzed in this work is thermosyphonic system.

Solar legislation in Israel distinguishes between vertical and horizontal storage tank [3].

In this work vertical storage tank is considered.

The system may include one solar collector or few solar collectors, in both cases this work defines the collector(s) array as a "collector".

Solar legislation in Israel requires installation of solar water heater in new buildings up to 9 floors, 27 meters from roof [3]. Thermosyphonic systems are usually installed up to 4 floors from roof. As the average, solar installation analyzed in this work is for residential unit 2 floors under roof.

National standards require thermal insulation for all hot water pipes of SWH [4]. As mentioned before, actually there is not any thermal insulation on circulation pipes. Hot water supply pipes locates inside the building are in sleeve made of LDPE.

Reverse circulation (reverse flow at night) is not considered as such analysis requires simulation program which is much beyond the scope of this work.

Specifications of SWH for the energy balance:

- Thermosyphonic system
- Open system (without heat exchanger)
- Storage tank volume 150 liters
- Storage tank position: vertical above solar collector
- Storage tank location: on roof, above solar collector and closest to solar collector
- Solar collector size 6,150 standard kcal/day
- All pipes: Pexgol XLPE 16 mm outside diameter
- No thermal insulation on any pipe
- Circulation pipes without any insulation or sleeve

- Hot water supply pipe in sleeve made of LDPE 22.2 inside diameter 25,0 outside diameter, 1.4 mm wall thickness
- Sleeve life time and properties till the end of the lifetime, same as storage tank and solar collector, at least 8 years, designed 20 years
- Backup: electric inside storage tank
- Location of residential unit: 2 floors under roof
- Effective arrangement to avoid reverse circulation (reverse natural flow after solar hours)

6. Energy Output of Solar Collector

The size of solar collector is expressed in kcal/day for standard conditions and not in m² [3].

The national solar standards determine the size of the solar collector according to the volume of the storage tank and according to the system type. For thermosyphonic systems with vertical storage tank, solar collector size is 41 kcal/d for each liter of the storage tank.

The size of the storage tank depends of the size of the residential unit.

According to the law the size of the storage tank for 4 rooms' apartment is 150 liter.

This determines the solar collector's size in our case:

Formula 1 - Size of solar collector

$$Q = 41 \text{ kcal/d,L} * 150 \text{ liter} = 6,150 \text{ kcal/day}$$

7. Monthly Changes of Solar Collector Energy

As mentioned before, the size of solar collector is determined for standard conditions. This includes standard solar radiation of 4,400 kcal/m²,d [3].

Formula 2 - Solar collector energy

$$Q = SE * Q / 4,400 \text{ kcal/m}^2, \text{d}$$

Q solar collector energy month average [kcal/d]
 SE global solar energy month average [kcal/m²,d]
 Q standard size of solar collector for 150 liters storage tank = 6,150 kcal/day
 4,400 kcal/m²,d standard solar radiation used for determination of the solar collector size

Table 3 - Solar collector energy each month

Month	SE	Q 150L	Q 150L
	kcal/m ² ,d	kcal/d	kWh/month
1	3,521	4,921	177
2	4,310	6,024	196
3	4,655	6,506	235
4	5,016	7,010	245
5	5,307	7,418	267
6	5,450	7,618	266
7	5,464	7,637	275
8	5,642	7,886	284
9	5,627	7,865	274
10	5,082	7,103	256
11	4,312	6,027	210
12	3,523	4,924	177
Ave	4,826	6,745	239
Σ/y			2,863

6,150 kcal/day size solar collector supplies equivalent of 2,863 kWh of energy per year.

8. Solar Collector Efficiency

Collector's efficiency is determined for standard conditions, including global radiation of 4,400 kcal/m²,day [3]. Lower solar radiation decreases the efficiency while higher radiation improves the efficiency. Most of the year the solar radiation in Israel is higher than the standard radiation used for determination of the solar collector efficiency, which means that most of the year the solar collector is more efficient than tested. In this work changes of the collector's efficiency will be neglected contributing to the conservativeness of the calculations.

9. City Water (Cold Water) Temperature

Most of the population of Israel is around Tel Aviv, which is much warmer in winter than Jerusalem. For conservative approach of the calculations Jerusalem temperatures will be considered, which will result in higher energy losses than the national average.

It is assumed that city water temperature is 3°C above the average ambient air temperature.

Table 4 - Monthly averages of city water temperature in Jerusalem

Month	Tout	Tc
	°C	°C
1	8.4	11.4
2	7.3	10.3
3	10.5	13.5
4	14.8	17.8
5	18.7	21.7
6	20.9	23.9
7	22.3	25.3
8	23.1	26.1
9	20.7	23.7
10	19.9	22.9
11	13.7	16.7
12	11.1	14.1
Ave	16.0	19.0
Max	23.1	26.1
Min	7.3	10.3

10. Storage Tank Average Temperature

Storage tank average temperature for calculations was determined in publication [1].

Storage tank average temperature is determined considering amount of energy entering it and the hot water volume.

Energy from solar collector is transferred to storage tank considering circulation pipe losses. In addition the storage tank itself loses energy with hours because of heat transfer through the tank's envelop.

Lower storage tank temperature results in lower losses in circulation pipes. Energy losses in circulations pipes and storage tank are determined in publication [1].

To develop formula for calculation of the energy stored in storage tank, we can start with definition of specific heat.

Specific heat is amount of energy required to rise the temperature of 1 kg of mass by 1°C.

Translation this definition to symbols results in the following formula:

Formula 3 - Definition of specific heat

$$c = E / (m * \Delta t)$$

E energy [kcal]

m mass [kg]

c specific heat [kcal/kg,°C]

Δt temperature rise caused by energy E [°C]

The following formula will be used very frequently in this work:

Formula 4 - Energy required to heat mass

$$E = m * c * \Delta t$$

In context of energy stored in storage tank the parameter are as follows:

E	energy stored in storage tank [kcal/d]
m	mass of water in storage tank [kg]
c	specific heat of water = 1 kcal/kg,°C
Δt	storage tank temperature rise caused by energy E [°C]

As the water density is 1 kg/liter, the water mass in kg is equal to the storage tank volume, 150 liters

$$m = 150 \text{ liters} * 1 \text{ kg/liter} = 150 \text{ kg}$$

The temperature rise Δt is the difference between the initial temperature of the water, which is the temperature of the city water, and the final storage tank temperature after heating the water with the solar collector energy.

$$\Delta t = T_{st} - T_c$$

T_{st}	final storage tank temperature after heating the water with the solar collector energy [°C]
T_c	temperature of the city water (cold water) [°C]

$$T_{st} = T_c + \Delta t$$

$$\Delta t = E / (m * c)$$

Formula 5 - Storage tank temperature

$$T_{st} = T_c + (E - \text{Losses}) / (m * c)$$

E	energy from solar collector [kcal/day]
Losses	energy losses [kcal/day]

Table 5 - Storage tank water temperature

Month	Tc	E	Losses	ΣE	Tst
	°C	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	°C
1	11.4	4,921	372	4,549	41.7
2	10.3	6,024	453	5,571	47.5
3	13.5	6,506	495	6,011	53.5
4	17.8	7,010	515	6,496	61.2
5	21.7	7,418	556	6,862	67.5
6	23.9	7,618	567	7,051	70.9
7	25.3	7,637	566	7,070	72.5
8	26.1	7,886	575	7,312	74.8
9	23.7	7,865	569	7,296	72.4
10	22.9	7,103	514	6,589	66.8
11	16.7	6,027	460	5,567	53.8
12	14.1	4,924	371	4,553	44.5
Ave					60.6
Max					74.8
Min					41.7

11. Circulation Hours

Solar hours are regarded from sunrise to sunset. Monthly data are based on 15th each month. Circulation stops before sunset when solar energy is too weak to cause the circulation.

Table 6 - Circulation hours on 15th each month in Jerusalem

Month	Sunrise	Sunset	Balance time	HRcirc hr/d
1	06:39	16:57	16:12	9.6
2	06:21	17:25	16:46	10.4
3	05:49	17:47	17:14	11.4
4	06:10	19:08	18:41	12.5
5	05:42	19:28	19:07	13.4
6	05:33	19:46	19:31	14.0
7	05:44	19:45	19:24	13.7
8	06:03	19:22	18:55	12.9
9	06:23	18:44	18:11	11.8
10	06:42	18:06	17:27	10.8
11	06:07	16:39	15:54	9.8
12	06:31	16:36	15:46	9.3

12. Ambient Temperatures in Circulation Hours

The ambient air temperatures are required for calculations of heat losses of circulation pipes.

The ambient temperature is not the month average but the average of the temperatures in the circulation hours, which are solar hours, T_{sun} .

Table 7 - Average ambient temperatures in solar hours in Jerusalem

Month	Tout	Tsun
1	8.4	9.7
2	7.3	8.9
3	10.5	12.3
4	14.8	16.9
5	18.7	20.6
6	20.9	23.3
7	22.3	24.5
8	23.1	25.4
9	20.7	22.9
10	19.9	21.7
11	13.7	15.4
12	11.1	13.1
Ave	16.0	17.9
Max	23.1	25.4
Min	7.3	8.9

13. Water Temperature in Circulation Pipes

Temperature of water supplied from solar collector to storage tank is higher than the storage tank average temperature. However water returning from the storage tank to the solar collector is colder than the storage tank average temperature. This justifies application of the average temperature of the storage tank water for heat transfer calculations.

The temperatures of water in storage tank, as calculated above, are on the end of the day. At the beginning of the day the temperature is slightly above the outside temperature. The average between these 2 extremes could result in an average between the outside temperature and the maximum temperature of the storage tank. However, at the beginning of the day the storage tank temperature is rising fast, and at the end of the day very slow. Therefore 2/3 of the temperature

difference will be applied in this work for the calculations of the daily average temperature of water in the storage tank.

Formula 6 - Temperature in the circulation pipes (Tcirc)

$$T_{circ} = T_c + (2/3) * (T_{st} - T_c)$$

Tcirc temperature in the circulation pipes

Tc city water temperature

Tst storage tank maximum temperature

Table 8 - Water temperature in circulation pipes

Month	Tc	Tst	Δt	Tpipe 50%	Tcirc 67%
	°C	°C	°C	°C	°C
1	11.4	41.7	30.3	26.5	31.6
2	10.3	47.5	37.1	28.9	35.1
3	13.5	53.5	40.1	33.5	40.2
4	17.8	61.2	43.3	39.5	46.7
5	21.7	67.5	45.7	44.6	52.2
6	23.9	70.9	47.0	47.4	55.3
7	25.3	72.5	47.1	48.9	56.8
8	26.1	74.8	48.7	50.5	58.6
9	23.7	72.4	48.6	48.1	56.2
10	22.9	66.8	43.9	44.8	52.2
11	16.7	53.8	37.1	35.2	41.4
12	14.1	44.5	30.4	29.3	34.4
Ave	19.0	60.6	41.6	39.8	46.7
Max		74.8	48.7	50.5	58.6
Min		41.7	30.3	26.5	31.6

Table 9 - Circulation pipes inside and outside temperatures

Month	Tcirc	Tsun	Δt
	°C	°C	°C
1	31.6	9.7	21.9
2	35.1	8.9	26.2
3	40.2	12.3	27.8
4	46.7	16.9	29.9
5	52.2	20.6	31.6
6	55.3	23.3	32.0
7	56.8	24.5	32.3
8	58.6	25.4	33.1
9	56.2	22.9	33.3
10	52.2	21.7	30.4
11	41.4	15.4	26.0
12	34.4	13.1	21.2
Ave	46.7	17.9	28.8

Tsun ambient temperature in circulation hours (in solar hours)

14. Hot Water Supply Temperature

Water supply temperature will be determined in this work as an average between the storage tank temperature and the useful temperature.

Useful temperature may be regarded 37°C.

Table 10 - Hot water supply temperature

Month	Tst	Δ to 37°C	Tsup
	°C	°C	°C
1	41.7	4.7	39.4
2	47.5	10.5	42.2
3	53.5	16.5	45.3
4	61.2	24.2	49.1
5	67.5	30.5	52.2
6	70.9	33.9	54.0
7	72.5	35.5	54.7
8	74.8	37.8	55.9
9	72.4	35.4	54.7
10	66.8	29.8	51.9
11	53.8	16.8	45.4
12	44.5	7.5	40.7
Ave	60.6	23.6	48.8

Hot water supply pipe in thermosyphonic system has the following parts:

- On the roof, from storage tank to the entrance to the building
- Vertical part between floors of building
- From entrance to the residential unit to shower's valve

14.1. Hot Water Supply Pipe on Roof

Pipe insulation according to the national standards is at least 19 mm [4].

Outside temperature for calculations of energy losses is the ambient temperature in evening, equivalent to the daily average temperature (T_{out}).

Table 11 - Hot water temperatures in supply pipe located outside

Month	T_{sup} °C	T_{out} °C	Δt °C
1	39.4	8.4	31.0
2	42.2	7.3	34.9
3	45.3	10.5	34.8
4	49.1	14.8	34.2
5	52.2	18.7	33.5
6	54.0	20.9	33.0
7	54.7	22.3	32.4
8	55.9	23.1	32.8
9	54.7	20.7	34.0
10	51.9	19.9	32.0
11	45.4	13.7	31.7
12	40.7	11.1	29.6
Ave	48.8	16.0	32.8

14.2. Hot Water Supply Pipe between Floors

Pipe insulation according to the national standards is at least 13 mm [4].

Outside temperature for calculations of energy losses will be regarded as building temperature, which is 4°C above the average air temperature ($T_b = T_{out} + 4^\circ\text{C}$).

Usually the passage of pipes in the building is not vented which increases the outside temperature of the pipe and decreases energy losses. This outside temperature increase of pipes in building will be not considered for thermosyphonic system, contributing to conservative approach of calculation.

Table 12 - Hot water supply pipe outside temperature in building

Month	Tout	Tb
	°C	°C
1	8.4	12.4
2	7.3	11.3
3	10.5	14.5
4	14.8	18.8
5	18.7	22.7
6	20.9	24.9
7	22.3	26.3
8	23.1	27.1
9	20.7	24.7
10	19.9	23.9
11	13.7	17.7
12	11.1	15.1
Ave	16.0	20.0
Max	23.1	27.1
Min	7.3	11.3

15. Water Flow

Typical hot water flow is 5 liters per minutes.

Table 13 - Water flow

Water flow	0.083	L/s
Water flow	5	liter/minute
Water flow	300	L/hr
Water flow	0.30	m3/hr

The above water flow is a mix of hot water and cold water resulting in 37°C, the temperature comfortable for shower. The mix depends on the storage tank temperature and the cold water temperature.

Following equations may be used to find the mix ratio:

$$x_c * T_c + x_h * T_h = 5 \text{ [L/min]} * 37^\circ\text{C}$$

$$x_c + x_h = 5 \text{ [L/min]}$$

x_c cold water flow [L/min]
 x_h hot water flow [L/min]
 T_c cold water temperature
 T_h hot water temperature

Formula 7 - Hot water mix ratio

$$xh \text{ [L/min]} = (185 - 5 * Tc) / (Th - Tc)$$

This formula allows calculations of time required to empty the storage tank.

This work distinguishes between energy E expressed in kcal and between energy Q of the water flow expressed in kcal/hour

$$Q \text{ [kcal/hr]} = E \text{ [kcal]} / \text{Time [hr]}$$

Application of the formula for storage tank will result in:

Formula 8 - Time to empty storage tank

$$\text{Time} = E / Q$$

$$Q = xh * (Th - Tc)$$

Time time to empty storage tank [hr]
 E energy stored in storage tank [kcal/day]
 Q energy of hot water flow in supply pipe [kcal/hr]

Table 14 - Time to empty storage tank

Month	Tc	Tsup	xh	Q	E	Time	Time
	°C	°C	L/min	kcal/min	kcal/d	minutes	hr
1	11.4	39.4	4.6	128	6,083	47	0.79
2	10.3	42.2	4.2	133	6,328	47	0.79
3	13.5	45.3	3.7	118	5,587	47	0.79
4	17.8	49.1	3.1	96	4,764	50	0.83
5	21.7	52.2	2.5	76	5,060	66	1.11
6	23.9	54.0	2.2	65	5,216	80	1.33
7	25.3	54.7	2.0	58	5,226	90	1.49
8	26.1	55.9	1.8	55	5,440	100	1.66
9	23.7	54.7	2.1	66	5,453	82	1.37
10	22.9	51.9	2.4	71	4,847	69	1.14
11	16.7	45.4	3.5	102	4,823	47	0.79
12	14.1	40.7	4.3	114	5,426	47	0.79
Ave	19.0	48.8	3.0	90.2	5354	64.4	1.07

16. Energy Demand for Hot Water

According to [3] [7] the use of hot water from 120 liters SWH is equivalent to 1,450 kWh/y. This is based on the Israel Electric Company surveys from years when electric water heaters had separate meters and switches to operate only in off-peak hours [6] [7].

The consumption of 120 liters electric heaters was 1,200 kWh/y as national average [3], [6], [7]. At the same time the consumption of electricity for backup of 120 liters solar water heaters was 250 kWh/y in average.

The estimation of use of 1,450 kWh/y for 120 liters SWH is related to the quality of life; families having solar water heater use more hot water than families having electric water heater, as the national average. The number 1,450 kWh/y for 120 liters SWH includes the 250 kWh/y electric backup.

SWH in size of 120 liters supplies 1,800 kWh equivalent of hot water per year [3] [7]. At the times of the surveys [6], [7] only 1,450 kWh/y were used and 350 kWh/y was wasted.

Daily demand for energy is not the result of dividing 1,450 kWh/y by 365 days in year. The energy depends on the difference between the water temperature required for shower, which is 37°C, and the city water temperature. The amount of hot water demand in liters per day is regarded in this work as constant (the same each month).

Table 15 - Use of energy for 150 liters SWH

Storage tank	Liters	120	150
Energy demand	kWh/y	1,450	1,813
Electric backup	kWh/y	250	313

Formula 9 - Energy demand for 1 liter of hot water

$$Ed = m * c * (37^{\circ}\text{C} - tc)$$

Ed energy demand [kcal/d,l]

m mass of water = 1 kg/day

c specific heat of water = 1 kcal/kg°C

tc city water (cold water) average month temperature [°C]

Table 16 - Energy demand for 1 liter of hot water

Month	Tc	Δ to 37°C	Ed	Ed	Ed
	°C	°C	kcal/d,L	kcal/month,L	kWh/month,L
1	11.4	25.6	25.6	794	0.9
2	10.3	26.7	26.7	746	0.9
3	13.5	23.5	23.5	730	0.8
4	17.8	19.2	19.2	575	0.7
5	21.7	15.3	15.3	473	0.6
6	23.9	13.1	13.1	393	0.5
7	25.3	11.7	11.7	362	0.4
8	26.1	10.9	10.9	338	0.4
9	23.7	13.3	13.3	398	0.5
10	22.9	14.1	14.1	438	0.5
11	16.7	20.3	20.3	610	0.7
12	14.1	22.9	22.9	709	0.8
Σ				6,565	7.6
Ave	19.0	18.0	18.0	547.1	0.6

Table 17 - Daily use of hot water

Storage tank	Liters	120	150
Ed	kWh/y	1,450	1,813
Ed	kWh/y,L	7.6	7.6
Water use	Liter/day	190	237
PE		3	4
Water use	Liter/PE,d	63	59

Ed energy demand

PE person, people equivalent

According to the Israeli legislation [3], 120 liters SWH is for 3 rooms residential unit and 150 liters for 4 rooms. As the average occupation of 4 rooms apartment is 4 people, this may result in about 60 liters of hot water per person per day.

17. Energy Losses

Following are the components of the losses:

- Loss of energy of hot water in circulation pipes (CircEW)
- Initial heating of circulation pipes and the insulation mass (CircM)
- Heat transfer in circulation pipes (CircHX)
- Loss of water in hot water supply pipe (SupEW)
- Initial heating of hot water supply pipe and the insulation mass (SupM)
- Heat transfer in hot water supply pipe (SupHT)
- Heat losses of storage tank (STHT)

Labels of losses in tables:

CircEW	- Circulation Energy in Water Losses
CircM	- Circulation Mass Losses
CircHX	- Circulation Heat Transfer
SupEW	- Supply Energy in Water Losses
SupM	- Supply Mass Losses
SupHX	- Supply Heat Transfer
STHX	- Storage Tank Heat Transfer
other	- other losses to meet electric backup according to the national statistics

18. Conservative Approach

Energy losses are determined using conservative approach, which means are over-estimated. However total losses including "other" losses are precisely determined applying data from national statistics.

19. Formulas, Input Values and Detailed Calculations

Formulas and input values for calculations are detailed in publication [2]. The publication [2] includes also detailed calculations of key parameters.

Following is Formula "Heat transfer considering sum of thermal resistance components" in publication [2]:

Formula 10 - Heat transfer considering sum of thermal resistance components

$$Q = (\pi * L * \Delta t) / \Sigma r$$

$$Q = L * \Delta t * (\pi / \Sigma r)$$

L pipe's length [meter]

Δt temperature difference between inside and outside of the pipe [°C]

$(\pi/\Sigma r)$ parameter is energy loss of insulated pipe 1 meter long, per hour, per 1°C [kcal/(meter, hour, °C)].

Table 18 - $(\pi/\Sigma r)$ parameter for insulated and not insulated pipes

Location	Water Flow	Insulation	Steel	XLPE	Application
		mm	kcal/ m°C,hr	kcal/ m°C,hr	
Outside	laminar	20	0.188	0.155	Thermosyphonic: Circulation
Outside	turbulent	20	0.189	0.156	Thermosyphonic: Supply pipe outside, Forced: Circulation outside
Inside	turbulent	13	0.207	0.169	Thermosyphonic: Supply pipe inside, Forced: Circulation inside, Forced: Supply pipe inside
Outside	laminar	0		0.890	Thermosyphonic: Circulation
Outside	turbulent	0		0.910	Thermosyphonic: Supply pipe outside
Inside	turbulent	Sleeve		0.136	Theoretical: Thermosyphonic: Supply pipe inside
Inside	turbulent	Sleeve		0.169	Practical: Thermosyphonic: Supply pipe inside

20. Pipes Length for Energy Balance

20.1. Circulation Pipes

Circulation pipes length applied for energy balance is 3 meters for both pipes together.

20.2. Hot Water Supply Pipe

Thermosyphonic solar water heaters are used in Israel up to 4 floors from roof. The average will be applied for energy balance which is 2 floors. Each floor is 3 meters high. 4 meters pipe's length will be added for roof and apartment, 2 meters on roof and 2 meters in apartment. Total pipe's length applied will be 10 meters.

21. Energy in Water Losses in Circulation Pipes (CircEW)

By the end of solar hours the circulation stops and all energy of hot water in circulation pipes is lost.

The initial temperature is city water temperature T_c .

The final temperature is storage tank temperature T_{st} .

Table 19 - Energy loss of hot water in circulation pipes (CircEW)

Month	Tc	Tst	Δt	CircEW	CircEW
	°C	°C	°C	kcal/d,meter	kcal/d
1	11.4	41.7	30.3	3.2	9.6
2	10.3	47.5	37.1	3.9	11.8
3	13.5	53.5	40.1	4.2	12.7
4	17.8	61.2	43.3	4.6	13.7
5	21.7	67.5	45.7	4.8	14.5
6	23.9	70.9	47.0	5.0	14.9
7	25.3	72.5	47.1	5.0	14.9
8	26.1	74.8	48.7	5.2	15.5
9	23.7	72.4	48.6	5.1	15.4
10	22.9	66.8	43.9	4.6	13.9
11	16.7	53.8	37.1	3.9	11.8
12	14.1	44.5	30.4	3.2	9.6
Ave	19.0	60.6	41.6	4.4	13.2

22. Initial Heating of Circulation Pipes Mass (CircM)

By the end of solar hours the circulation will stop and all energy of circulation pipes mass will be lost.

The initial temperature is city water temperature Tc.

The final temperature is storage tank temperature Tst.

Input values for calculations of initial heating of circulation pipe mass are detailed in publication [2] Section "Initial Heating of Pipe and Insulation Mass".

Table 20 - Input values for calculations of initial heating of circulation pipe mass

length	100	cm
din1	1.16	cm
dout1	1.60	cm
volume pipe	95	cm ³
density pipe	0.94	g/cm ³
weight pipe	89	g
weight pipe	0.1	kg
c pipe	0.55	kcal/kg,°C
E pipe	0.05	kcal/°C

Initial temperature is city water temperature Tc.

Final temperature is storage tank temperature Tst.

Table 21 - Initial heating of circulation pipes' mass

Month	T _c	T _{st}	Δt	CircM	CircM
	°C	°C	°C	kcal/m,d	kcal/d
1	11.4	41.7	30.3	1.5	4.5
2	10.3	47.5	37.1	1.8	5.5
3	13.5	53.5	40.1	2.0	5.9
4	17.8	61.2	43.3	2.1	6.4
5	21.7	67.5	45.7	2.2	6.7
6	23.9	70.9	47.0	2.3	6.9
7	25.3	72.5	47.1	2.3	6.9
8	26.1	74.8	48.7	2.4	7.2
9	23.7	72.4	48.6	2.4	7.2
10	22.9	66.8	43.9	2.2	6.5
11	16.7	53.8	37.1	1.8	5.5
12	14.1	44.5	30.4	1.5	4.5
Ave	19.0	60.6	41.6	2.0	6.1

23. Heat Transfer in Circulation Pipes (CircHX)

Input values are detailed in publication [1] Section "Heat Transfer in 1 Meter Circulation Pipe Located Outside".

Table 22 - Input data for heat transfer calculations

L	1	m
α_{in}	1,000	kcal/m ² °C,hr
d _{in1}	0.012	m
d _{out1}	0.016	m
λ_1	0.301	kcal/m°°C,hr
α_{out}	21.496	kcal/m ² °C,hr

Circulation pipe is not insulated and has only one solid layer (λ_1), plastic XLPE pipe.

Table 23 - Thermal resistance elements of circulation pipe

Element	Formula	Resistance	Unit	%
Inside laminar layer	$[1 / (\alpha_{in} * d_{in1})]$	0.09	m°°C,hr/kcal	2.4%
XLPE pipe	$[\text{Ln}(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \lambda_1)]$	0.53	m°°C,hr/kcal	15.1%
Outside laminar layer	$[1 / (\alpha_{out} * d_{out1})]$	2.91	m°°C,hr/kcal	82.4%
Σr	3	3.53	m°°C,hr/kcal	100.0%

Table 24 - $(\pi/\Sigma r)$ parameter for circulation pipe

Σr	m°C,hr/kcal	3.53
$\pi/\Sigma r$	kcal/m°C,hr	0.890

Table 25 - Heat transfer in circulation pipes (CircHX)

Month	Tcirc °C	Tsun °C	Δt °C	HRcirc hr/d	CircHX kcal/meter,d	CircHX kcal/d
1	31.6	9.7	21.9	9.6	186	559
2	35.1	8.9	26.2	10.4	243	730
3	40.2	12.3	27.8	11.4	283	850
4	46.7	16.9	29.9	12.5	333	999
5	52.2	20.6	31.6	13.4	378	1,133
6	55.3	23.3	32.0	14.0	398	1,193
7	56.8	24.5	32.3	13.7	393	1,179
8	58.6	25.4	33.1	12.9	380	1,139
9	56.2	22.9	33.3	11.8	350	1,049
10	52.2	21.7	30.4	10.8	292	875
11	41.4	15.4	26.0	9.8	227	681
12	34.4	13.1	21.2	9.3	175	525
Ave	46.7	17.9	28.8	11.6	303	910

24. Energy of Hot Water in Water Supply Pipe (SupEW)

Hot water supply pipe in thermosyphonic system has the following parts:

- On roof, from storage tank to entrance to the building
- Vertical part between floors of building
- From entrance to the residential unit to shower's valve

2 floors from room distance will be applied to energy balance. Each floor is 3 meters high. 2 meters of pipe are on roof and 2 meters of pipe are in residential unit. Total length of hot water supply pipe is applied for calculations 10 meters, of which 2 meters are located outside on roof, and 8 meters inside the building.

24.1. Hot Water Supply Pipe on Roof, SupEWout

The pipe is not insulated and not in sleeve. 2 meters of pipe's length is applied for calculations.

Outside temperature for calculations of energy losses will be regarded as daily average of air ambient temperature, T_{out} .

Inside temperature is the minimum useful temperature at the end of the use of hot water from storage tank, which is 37°C .

Table 26 - Energy losses in hot water in supply pipe located outside, SupEWout

Month	T_{out} $^{\circ}\text{C}$	Δ to 37°C $^{\circ}\text{C}$	SupEWout kcal/d, meter	SupEWout kcal/d
1	8.4	28.6	3.0	6.1
2	7.3	29.7	3.1	6.3
3	10.5	26.5	2.8	5.6
4	14.8	22.2	2.3	4.7
5	18.7	18.3	1.9	3.9
6	20.9	16.1	1.7	3.4
7	22.3	14.7	1.6	3.1
8	23.1	13.9	1.5	2.9
9	20.7	16.3	1.7	3.4
10	19.9	17.1	1.8	3.6
11	13.7	23.3	2.5	4.9
12	11.1	25.9	2.7	5.5
Ave	16.0	21.0	2.2	4.4

24.2. Hot Water Supply Pipe inside Building, SupEWin

Pipe is in plastic sleeve with air gap.

Outside temperature for calculations of energy losses will be regarded as building temperature, which is 4°C above the average air temperature ($T_b = T_{out} + 4^{\circ}\text{C}$).

Usually the passage of pipes in buildings is not vented which increases outside temperature of the pipe and decreases energy losses. This outside temperature increase of pipe in building will be not considered for thermosyphonic system, contributing to conservative approach of calculation.

Hot water supply pipe in residential unit has low energy losses in winter because of space heating in the residential unit. However, considering conservative approach of the calculations, this part of the pipe will be regarded as inside the building.

Table 27 - Hot water supply pipe outside temperature in building, Tb

Month	Tout	Tb
	°C	°C
1	8.4	12.4
2	7.3	11.3
3	10.5	14.5
4	14.8	18.8
5	18.7	22.7
6	20.9	24.9
7	22.3	26.3
8	23.1	27.1
9	20.7	24.7
10	19.9	23.9
11	13.7	17.7
12	11.1	15.1
Ave	16.0	20.0
Max	23.1	27.1
Min	7.3	11.3

 Table 28 - Energy loss of water in supply pipe, 8 meters inside the building, SupEWin

Month	Tb	Δ to 37°C	SupEWin	SupEWin
	°C	°C	kcal/d, meter	kcal/d
1	12.4	24.6	2.6	20.8
2	11.3	25.7	2.7	21.7
3	14.5	22.5	2.4	19.1
4	18.8	18.2	1.9	15.3
5	22.7	14.3	1.5	12.1
6	24.9	12.1	1.3	10.2
7	26.3	10.7	1.1	9.0
8	27.1	9.9	1.0	8.4
9	24.7	12.3	1.3	10.4
10	23.9	13.1	1.4	11.1
11	17.7	19.3	2.0	16.3
12	15.1	21.9	2.3	18.5
Ave	20.0	17.0	1.8	14.4

24.3. Total Losses of Hot Water in Supply Pipe, SupEWTable 29 - Total losses of hot water in supply pipe, SupEW, for 2 floors under roof

Month	SupHXout	SupHXin	Σ
Length, m	2	8	10
	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d
1	39.8	23.3	63.1
2	46.1	26.6	72.8
3	47.0	26.6	73.5
4	49.7	27.7	77.4
5	49.5	36.1	85.6
6	49.6	42.8	92.3
7	48.6	47.0	95.6
8	48.2	53.1	101.4
9	48.3	45.4	93.7
10	44.0	35.5	79.5
11	40.1	23.9	64.0
12	37.3	22.1	59.4

25. **Initial Heating of Hot Water Supply Pipe's Mass (SupM)**Table 30 - Input values for calculations of initial heating of hot water supply pipe's mass

Length	100	cm
din1	1.16	cm
dout1	1.60	cm
Volume pipe	95	cm ³
density pipe	0.94	g/cm ³
weight pipe	89	g
weight pipe	0.1	kg
c pipe	0.55	kcal/kg, °C
E pipe	0.05	kcal/°C

Applied outside temperature is T_{out} , including pipe inside building, which should be calculated based on building temperature, T_b . This approach is conservative (results in higher losses).

Table 31 - Initial heating of hot water supply pipe's mass (SupM) for 2 floors under roof

Month	Tout °C	Δ to 37°C °C	SupM kcal/d, meter	SupM kcal/d
1	8.4	28.6	1.4	14.1
2	7.3	29.7	1.5	14.6
3	10.5	26.5	1.3	13.0
4	14.8	22.2	1.1	10.9
5	18.7	18.3	0.9	9.0
6	20.9	16.1	0.8	7.9
7	22.3	14.7	0.7	7.2
8	23.1	13.9	0.7	6.8
9	20.7	16.3	0.8	8.0
10	19.9	17.1	0.8	8.4
11	13.7	23.3	1.1	11.5
12	11.1	25.9	1.3	12.7
Ave	16.0	21.0	1.0	10.3

26. Heat Transfer in Hot Water Supply Pipe (SupHX)

26.1. Sleeve for Hot Water Supply Pipe

This work considers that a part of hot water supply pipe located outside on roof is without thermal insulation and not in sleeve.

Part of hot water supply pipe located inside the building is also without thermal insulation but in plastic sleeve.

The plastic sleeve is related more for the building construction technology than to energy conservation. The same sleeve is used also for cold water pipes, which do not require any insulation.

The plastic sleeve is LDPE pipe for electric cables. Its inner diameter is bigger than the supply pipe outside diameter, which creates air gap between the hot water supply pipe and the sleeve. The air gap substitutes thermal insulation.

The sleeve's inside diameter is 22.2 mm containing 16 mm OD plastic hot water supply pipe. Outside diameter of the sleeve is 25.0 mm. Wall thickness of the sleeve is 1.4 mm.

The plastic sleeve is made of durable material which should have a lifetime as the lifetime of the building.

26.2. Heat Transfer Formula for Pipe in Sleeve

The formula was developed in publication [2] in Section "*Sleeve Instead of Insulation*".

Formula 11 - Thermal resistance of water pipe, sleeve and laminar layers

$$RA = r_{Ain1} + r_{A1} + r_{Aout1} + r_{Ain2} + r_{A2} + r_{Aout2}$$

R total thermal resistance of the pipe and sleeve assembly
 r thermal resistance of single layer
 $r_{Ain1} + r_{A1} + r_{Aout1}$ are related to the water pipe
 $r_{Ain2} + r_{A2} + r_{Aout2}$ are related to the sleeve
 r_{A1} rA of water pipe
 r_{A2} rA of sleeve
 r_{Ainx}, r_{Aoutx} rA of laminar layers

Formula 12 - Heat transfer through water pipe and sleeve with air gap

$$Q = (\pi * L * \Delta t) / \{ [1 / (\alpha_{in1} * d_{in1})] + [\ln(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \lambda_1)] + \\ + [1 / (\alpha_{out1} * d_{out1})] + [1 / (\alpha_{in2} * d_{in2})] \\ + [\ln(d_{out2}/d_{in2}) / (2 * \lambda_2)] + [1 / (\alpha_{out2} * d_{out2})] \}$$

Index 1 is related to the water pipe, and index 2 is related to the sleeve.

α_{out1} and α_{in2} are for air trapped between the water pipe and the sleeve.

26.3. Heat Transfer In Water Supply Pipe Located Inside (SupHXin)

26.3.1. Input Values

Input values were determined in publication [2]:

Table 32 - Input values for calculations of heat transfer of 1 meter of hot water supply pipe and sleeve

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Length	L	1.000	m
Water pipe Dia In	din1	0.0116	m
Water pipe Dia Out	dout1	0.0160	m
Sleeve Dia In din2	din2	0.0222	m
Sleeve Dia Out	dout2	0.0250	m
Pipe laminar layer In	α_{in1}	10,000	kcal/m ² °C,hr
Pipe laminar layer Out	α_{out1}	6.61	kcal/m ² °C,hr
Sleeve laminar layer In	α_{in2}	6.61	kcal/m ² °C,hr
Sleeve laminar layer Out	α_{out2}	21.50	kcal/m ² °C,hr
Conductivity pipe	λ_1	0.301	kcal/m°C,hr
Conductivity sleeve	λ_2	0.284	kcal/m°C,hr

26.3.2. Thermal Resistance Elements

Table 33 - Thermal resistance of elements of water supply pipe and sleeve assembly

Element	Formula	Resistance	Unit	%
Water laminar layer	$[1 / (\alpha_{in1} * din1)]$	0.01	m°C,hr/kcal	0.0%
Water pipe material	$[Ln(dout1/din1) / (2 * \lambda_1)]$	0.53	m°C,hr/kcal	2.3%
Water pipe out layer	$[1 / (\alpha_{out1} * dout1)]$	9.45	m°C,hr/kcal	41.0%
Sleeve in laminar layer	$[1 / (\alpha_{in2} * din2)]$	6.81	m°C,hr/kcal	29.5%
Sleeve material	$[Ln(dout2/din2) / (2 * \lambda_2)]$	0.21	m°C,hr/kcal	0.9%
Sleeve out laminar layer	$[1 / (\alpha_{out2} * dout2)]$	6.05	m°C,hr/kcal	26.2%
Σr	6	23.06	m°C,hr/kcal	100.0%

The sleeve solution gives better theoretical results than thermal insulation.

Σr for thermal insulation is 18.61 m°C,hr/kcal

Table 34 - Comparison of theoretical thermal resistance between sleeve and thermal insulation

	Σr
	$m^{\circ}C,hr/kcal$
Sleeve	23.06
Thermal insulation	18.61
Δ	24%

The above comparison is based on an assumption that the water pipe is concentric with the sleeve and there is air gap all around the water pipe. This is not the actual situation, as always some part of the water pipe has contact with the sleeve. In vertical pipe, there is less opportunities for such situation, however for horizontal pipe the contact caused by the water pipe weight including the weight of water, is on the whole length of the lower part of the pipe. Sometimes the weight of building materials for floor causes additional contact at the upper side of the horizontal pipe. Such contacts damage the air gap layers, which are the main components of the thermal resistance of the assembly. Bigger is the wall thickness of the sleeve, less harm is done to the sleeve. On the other hand, also thermal insulation may loose its thickness in horizontal pipes under weight of construction materials, which can reduce its thermal resistance.

Considering the above, it is estimated that the practical thermal resistance of sleeve solution is equal to theoretical thermal resistance of insulation, which is 18.61 $m^{\circ}C,hr/kcal$.

Table 35 - Thermal resistance and conductivity of hot water supply pipe and sleeve

		SupHXin
Σr Theoretical	$m^{\circ}C,hr/kcal$	23.06
Σr Practical	$m^{\circ}C,hr/kcal$	18.61
$\pi/\Sigma r$ Thoretical	$kcal/m^{\circ}C,hr$	0.136
$\pi/\Sigma r$ Practical	$kcal/m^{\circ}C,hr$	0.169

Table 36 - Heat transfer in hot water supply pipe located in building (SupHXin)

Month	T _b °C	T _{sup} °C	Δt °C	HR _{sup} hr/d	SupHXin kcal/d, meter	SupHXin kcal/d
1	12.4	39.4	27.0	0.8	3.6	28.8
2	11.3	42.2	30.9	0.8	4.1	33.0
3	14.5	45.3	30.8	0.8	4.1	32.9
4	18.8	49.1	30.2	0.8	4.3	34.3
5	22.7	52.2	29.5	1.1	5.6	44.7
6	24.9	54.0	29.0	1.4	6.6	53.0
7	26.3	54.7	28.4	1.5	7.3	58.3
8	27.1	55.9	28.8	1.7	8.2	65.9
9	24.7	54.7	30.0	1.4	7.0	56.3
10	23.9	51.9	28.0	1.2	5.5	44.0
11	17.7	45.4	27.7	0.8	3.7	29.6
12	15.1	40.7	25.6	0.8	3.4	27.4

26.4. Heat Transfer In Water Supply Pipe Located Outside (SupHXout)

Short part of the hot water supply pipe is located on roof. This pipe is not in sleeve and is not insulated. 2 meters of this outside part of hot water supply pipe are applied for calculations.

Heat transfer in hot water supply pipe is different from circulation pipe. In circulation pipe water flow inside the pipe is slow, caused by natural thermosyphonic force. In water supply pipe the flow is much faster caused by city water pressure. This affects the thermal resistance of water laminar layer inside the water pipe.

Table 37 - Input data for heat transfer calculations in hot water supply pipe located outside

L	1	m
α_{in}	10,000	kcal/m ² °C,hr
d _{in1}	0.012	m
d _{out1}	0.016	m
λ_1	0.301	kcal/m°°C,hr
α_{out}	21.496	kcal/m ² °C,hr

Table 38 - Thermal resistance of uninsulated water supply plastic pipe located outside

Element	Formula	Resistance	unit	%
Inside laminar layer	$[1 / (\alpha_{in} * d_{in1})]$	0.01	m°C,hr/kcal	0.2%
XLPE pipe	$[\text{Ln}(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \lambda_1)]$	0.53	m°C,hr/kcal	15.5%
Outside laminar layer	$[1 / (\alpha_{out} * d_{out1})]$	2.91	m°C,hr/kcal	84.3%
Σr	3	3.45	m°C,hr/kcal	100.0%

The main component of thermal resistance of uninsulated pipe is its outside air laminar layer.

 Table 39 - $(\pi/\Sigma r)$ parameter for uninsulated water supply pipe located outside

Σr	m°C,hr/kcal	3.45
$\pi/\Sigma r$	kcal/m°C,hr	0.910

 Table 40 - Heat transfer of uninsulated pipe located outside – 2 meters (SupHXout)

Month	Tout °C	Tsup °C	Δt °C	HRsup hr/d	SupHXout kcal/d,meter	SupHXout kcal/d
1	8.4	39.4	31.0	0.8	22.3	44.6
2	7.3	42.2	34.9	0.8	25.1	50.3
3	10.5	45.3	34.8	0.8	25.1	50.2
4	14.8	49.1	34.2	0.8	26.2	52.4
5	18.7	52.2	33.5	1.1	34.2	68.5
6	20.9	54.0	33.0	1.4	40.6	81.3
7	22.3	54.7	32.4	1.5	44.8	89.6
8	23.1	55.9	32.8	1.7	50.5	101.1
9	20.7	54.7	34.0	1.4	43.0	86.1
10	19.9	51.9	32.0	1.2	33.9	67.8
11	13.7	45.4	31.7	0.8	22.8	45.7
12	11.1	40.7	29.6	0.8	21.3	42.7

26.5. Total Heat Transfer in Hot Water Supply Pipe (SupHX)Table 41 - Total heat transfer in hot water supply pipe (SupHX)

Month	SupHXout	SupHXin	Σ
Length, m	2	8	10
	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d
1	44.6	28.8	73.5
2	50.3	33.0	83.3
3	50.2	32.9	83.1
4	52.4	34.3	86.8
5	68.5	44.7	113.2
6	81.3	53.0	134.3
7	89.6	58.3	147.9
8	101.1	65.9	167.0
9	86.1	56.3	142.4
10	67.8	44.0	111.8
11	45.7	29.6	75.3
12	42.7	27.4	70.0

2 meters of uninsulated hot water supply pipe on roof loses 50% more energy than 8 meters of pipe in sleeve inside the building.

27. **Storage Tank Heat Transfer (STHX)**

Detailed calculations of storage tank heat transfer may be found in publication [1].

Table 42 - Storage tank heat transfer)

Month	QstCirc	EstMax	Qst	Est
	kcal/day	kcal/day	kcal/day	kcal/month
1	282	319	601	18,638
2	377	358	736	20,606
3	443	358	801	24,846
4	524	289	813	24,387
5	598	275	874	27,084
6	631	254	885	26,554
7	624	263	887	27,484
8	604	308	911	28,249
9	556	362	917	27,522
10	459	376	835	25,895
11	353	408	761	22,830
12	264	341	605	18,741
Σ/y				292,836

28. "Other" Losses

According to [3] [6] [7] 120 liters SWH uses electric backup 250 kWh/y.

Extrapolation for 150 liters SWH results in 312.5 kWh/y.

The backup electricity consumption data are per year and not per month.

Analysis was performed to find what should be the value of "other" losses each month that would result in backup as in the national statistics. "Other" losses are considered constant every month, as it is no other guess.

In summer, the excessive energy from SWH covers all of the irregular activities, however in winter backup is needed in the following cases:

- rainy days, heavy clouds, days with solar radiation less than month average
- extra demand for hot water, more than average
- reverse thermosyphonic flow after solar hours (hot water from storage tank is circulated through cold solar collector)
- loss of energy in solar collector which is not transferred to storage tank after balance hour (balance between the energy form solar collector and heat exchange losses)

29. Sum of Losses

29.1. Calculated Losses not Including "Other" Losses

Table 43 - Sum of calculated losses, 2 floors from roof, not including "other" losses

Month	CircEW	CircM	CircHX	SupEW	SupM	SupHX	STHX	Σ
	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d
1	10	4	559	27	14	73	625	1,312
2	12	5	730	28	15	83	751	1,624
3	13	6	850	25	13	83	812	1,801
4	14	6	999	20	11	87	823	1,960
5	15	7	1,133	16	9	113	880	2,172
6	15	7	1,193	14	8	134	891	2,262
7	15	7	1,179	12	7	148	892	2,260
8	15	7	1,139	11	7	167	915	2,262
9	15	7	1,049	14	8	142	920	2,156
10	14	6	875	15	8	112	843	1,873
11	12	5	681	21	11	75	774	1,580
12	10	4	525	24	13	70	628	1,274
Ave	14	6	944	18	10	111	829	1,933
%	1%	0%	49%	1%	1%	6%	43%	100%

CircEW	Circulation Pipes Energy for Water Heating
CircM	Circulation Pipes Mass Losses
CircHX	Circulation Pipes Heat Transfer
SupEW	Supply Pipe Energy for Water Heating
SupM	Supply Pipe Mass Losses
SupHX	Supply Pipe Heat Transfer
STHX	Storage Tank Heat Transfer
other	other losses, determined to meet the national statistics of SWH's actual backup

As indicated in the above table, energy losses in circulation pipes are almost the same as losses from storage tank, most of this because of uninsulated circulation pipe.

Fortunately, the losses in uninsulated pipes in winter are much lower than in summer, because of low water temperature in circulation pipes.

Chart 3 - Heat transfer losses in uninsulated circulation pipes, kcal/day

29.2. Energy Losses Including "Other" Losses – Yearly Averages

Chart 4 - Energy losses of SWH with uninsulated pipes - yearly average

Energy losses of 5 meters of uninsulated pipe on the roof are the main source of losses and are higher than storage tank losses as the yearly average.

The above presentation of losses is somehow confusing, because most of the losses are in summer, when SWH supplies more hot water than needed. Therefore next paragraph includes the same chart for January, when pipe's energy losses directly influence need for electric backup. Even so, in January uninsulated pipes losses are similar to storage tank losses, 30% of total losses.

29.3. Energy Losses Including "Other" Losses – January

Table 44 - Energy losses of SWH, kcal/day

kcal/d	Ave/y	January
Uninsulated pipes on roof 5 meters	1,031	618
Pipes in sleeve 8 meters	72	70
Storage Tank	829	625
"Other" losses	743	743
Σ	1,933	1,312

Chart 5 - Energy losses of SWH with uninsulated pipes in January

30. Energy Balance of SWH

30.1. Yearly Balance

Table 45 - Energy balance of thermosyphonic SWH with uninsulated pipes, 2 floors from roof, kcal/day

Month	Demand	SE from collector	Calculated losses	other losses	SE in tap	need for backup	Total energy available	not used
	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d
1	6,083	4,921	1,312	743	2,866	3,217	6,083	0
2	6,328	6,024	1,624	743	3,657	2,672	6,328	0
3	5,587	6,506	1,801	743	3,963	1,624	5,587	0
4	4,546	7,010	1,960	743	4,308	238	4,546	0
5	3,623	7,418	2,172	743	3,623	0	4,503	880
6	3,107	7,618	2,262	743	3,107	0	4,613	1,507
7	2,771	7,637	2,260	743	2,771	0	4,634	1,863
8	2,591	7,886	2,262	743	2,591	0	4,882	2,291
9	3,150	7,865	2,156	743	3,150	0	4,966	1,817
10	3,354	7,103	1,873	743	3,354	0	4,487	1,133
11	4,823	6,027	1,580	743	3,703	1,120	4,823	0
12	5,426	4,924	1,274	743	2,908	2,519	5,426	0
Ave	4,282	6,745	1,878	743	3,333	949	5,073	791
	84%	133%	37%	15%	66%	19%	100%	16%

"Other" losses are uncalculated losses.

To meet the data from national statistics for backup of solar water heaters, "other" losses should be 743 kcal/day, same value for each month.

Table 46 - Energy balance of thermosyphonic SWH with uninsulated pipes, 2 floor under roof, kWh/month

Month	Demand	SE from collector	Calculated losses	other losses	Available from SE	SE in tap	need for backup	Total energy available	not used
	kWh/month	kWh/month	kWh/month	kWh/month	kWh/month	kWh/month	kWh/month	kWh/month	kWh/month
1	219	177	47	27	103	103	116	219	0
2	206	196	53	24	119	119	87	206	0
3	201	235	65	27	143	143	59	201	0
4	159	245	68	26	150	150	8	159	0
5	131	267	78	27	162	131	0	162	32
6	108	266	79	26	161	108	0	161	53
7	100	275	81	27	167	100	0	167	67
8	93	284	82	27	176	93	0	176	83
9	110	274	75	26	173	110	0	173	63
10	121	256	68	27	162	121	0	162	41
11	168	210	55	26	129	129	39	168	0
12	196	178	46	27	105	105	91	196	0
Σ/y	1,813	2,864	798	315	1,751	1,413	400	2,151	338
	84%	133%	37%	15%	81%	66%	19%	100%	16%

Table 47 - Need for backup: insulated and uninsulated pipes

Insulated	293	kWh/y
Uninsulated	400	kWh/y
Δ	107	kWh/y
Δ	36%	

Table 48 - Available from solar energy in January

Insulated	3.8	kWh/d
Uninsulated	3.3	kWh/d
Δ	-0.4	kWh/d
Δ	-12%	

Chart 6 - Demand for energy and available energy supplied from SHW, kWh/day

Table 49 - Analysis of the results

Month	Demand	SE Insulated	SE Uninsulated	Backup Insulated	Backup Uninsulated	Δ SE	Δ Backup
	kWh/d	kWh/d	kWh/d	kWh/d	kWh/d	%	%
1	7.1	3.9	3.3	3.2	3.7	-14%	17%
2	7.4	5.0	4.3	2.4	3.1	-14%	30%
3	6.5	5.4	4.6	1.1	1.9	-15%	77%
4	5.3	6.0	5.0	0.0	0.3	-16%	#N/A
5	4.2	6.3	5.2	0.0	0.0	-17%	#N/A
6	3.6	6.5	5.4	0.0	0.0	-18%	#N/A
7	3.2	6.5	5.4	0.0	0.0	-18%	#N/A
8	3.0	6.8	5.7	0.0	0.0	-17%	#N/A
9	3.7	6.8	5.8	0.0	0.0	-15%	#N/A
10	3.9	6.1	5.2	0.0	0.0	-14%	#N/A
11	5.6	5.0	4.3	0.6	1.3	-13%	102%
12	6.3	3.9	3.4	2.4	2.9	-13%	21%

Negative influence of uninsulated pipes:

- Need for electric backup for additional month (April)
- Addition of 107 kWh/y for electric backup (36%)
- 12% less available energy in January

Chart 7 - Energy balance of 150 liters SWH, uninsulated plastic pipes, 2 floors from roof, yearly balance

Chart 8 - Energy balance of 150 liters SWH, 2 floors from roof, yearly balance, insulated and uninsulated plastic pipes

30.2. Energy Balance in January

Chart 9 - Energy losses of SWH with uninsulated pipes in January

Losses from 5 meters uninsulated pipe on roof are almost the same as losses of the storage tank.

Chart 10 - Energy balance of SWH with uninsulated pipes in January

31. Application of Plastic Sleeve on Outside Pipes

Hot water supply pipes inside building are in plastic sleeve. The sleeve inside diameter is 22.2 mm, leaving some space for 16 mm OD hot water pipe. The sleeve outside diameter is 25 mm.

The following sections include analysis of influence of application of such sleeve on pipes located outside on roof for:

- pipes between solar collector and storage tank
- exposed (not in sleeve) part of hot water supply pipe

32. National Impact

Thermosyphonic 150 liters SWH with plastic pipes needs 293 kWh/y electric backup [1].

As calculated before, 5 meters of uninsulated pipe on roof increases demand for backup by 107 kWh/y (36%) to 400 kWh/y.

There are more than 2 millions residential units in Israel with SWH. Considering that all of them have not thermal insulation on external pipes in few years after installation, the increased demand for backup results in waste of over 200 million kWh per year.

Electricity tariff for domestic sector was in year 2017 0.13 \$/kWh excluding VAT (ex VAT), flat for all hours and all days.

Backup for SWH is needed at peak hours. Peak hours' tariffs are much higher.

Surveys of electricity consumption in domestic sector 1973 and 1979 prepared by Israel Electric Company [6] [7] showed that peak backup for SWH is at 18:00 o'clock (comparing to 19:00 general winter peak).

Backup is needed from November till April. Following are relevant tariffs:

Table 50 - Peak tariffs at 18:00 hour

ex VAT	NIS/kWh	USD/kWh
Nov	0.4838	0.1344
Dec	0.9581	0.2661
Jan	0.9581	0.2661
Feb	0.9581	0.2661
Mar	0.4838	0.1344
Apr	0.4838	0.1344
Ave	0.7210	0.2003
Domestic	0.4726	0.1313

The average peak tariff for relevant time and months is 0.20 USD/kWh.

Table 51 - Waste of energy for national economy in kWh per year

Waste per residential unit	107	kWh/y
Residential units	2,000,000	
National waste of electricity	213,606,349	kWh/y

Table 52 - Waste of energy for national economy in USD per year

Tariff ex VAT		Domestic	Peak
Tariff	USD/kWh	0.1313	0.2003
Waste per residential unit	USD/y	14.02	21.39
National waste of electricity	USD/y	28,041,767	42,777,638

33. Economic Evaluation

The simplest and cheapest solution is plastic sleeve (plastic pipe).

The cost of sleeve is 0.37 USD/meter. Adding labor cost and contractor's profit results in final cost about 1 USD/meter.

Table 53 - Input data for economic evaluation

Sleeve cost	0.37	USD/meter
Labor cost	0.37	USD/meter
Contractor's profit	0.27	USD/meter
Contractor's profit	36%	
Total cost of sleeve	1.00	USD/meter
Pipe's length on roof	5	meter
Total cost of sleeve	5	USD
National cost	10,000,000	USD
Labor cost	3,666,667	USD
Labor cost	10	USD/hr

Table 54 - Economic evaluation

Input data for the national economy were applied to online calculator: "Economic Evaluation of Energy Conservation Projects" [5] resulting in the following printout:

Nowarski Engineering: New Technologies for Green Development: Energy	
Economic Evaluation of Energy Cons Capital Recovery Fact	
change any field with frame, all the rest will be	
Rate of Interest (ROI) [%/year]	4
life expectancy of the energy conservation project [years]	10
Investment in energy conservation project (I) [\$]	10000000
Energy Saving [\$ /year]	42777638
Capital Recovery Factor (CRF)	0.12
Present Value of yearly savings (PV) [\$]	346964963.50
Net Present Value of yearly savings (NPV) [\$]	336964963.50
PV/I [%]	3470%
Profit (PV/I-1) [%]	3370%
Max no loss Investment [\$]	346964964

Table 55 - Results of the economic evaluation

Rate of Interest	4%	%/year
Life expectancy of the project	10	years
Investment in project (I)	10,000,000	USD
Energy Saving	42,777,638	USD/y
Return of investment	0.23	years
Return of investment	2.81	months
Capital Recovery Factor (CRF)	0.12	
Present Value (PV)	346,964,964	USD
Net Present Value (NPV)	336,964,964	USD
PV/I	3470%	
Profit (PV/I-1)	3370%	
Creation of jobs	377,143	hours
Creation of jobs	189	people/year

34. References

1. Energy Balance of Solar Water Heaters: Thermosyphonic Systems – Joseph Nowarski, DOI:10.6084/m9.figshare.21509856
2. Heat Transfer in Solar Water Heaters Pipes: Thermosyphonic Systems – Joseph Nowarski, DOI:281/zenodo.17007309
3. Solar Israel – A practical and legislative model – Joseph Nowarski, Renewable Energy World, March-April 2000, p93-99, DOI: 10.6084/m9.figshare.21443073
4. Israeli Standard SI 579 part 6: Solar water heating systems: Pumped domestic systems (Forced Circulation Systems for Residential Units) – December 1998
5. Online calculator: Economic Evaluation of Energy Conservation Projects
<http://www.geocities.ws/nowarski/calculators/CRF.html>
6. Domestic Electricity Consumption Surveys 1973, 1979 - Israel Electric Company
7. Economic Evaluation of Thermosyphonic Solar Water Heaters in Israel – Emanuel Zabłudowski – Ministry of Energy / Energy Conservation Department, 1980?

* * *